

LINGVOPRAGMATIC COMPETENCE IS AN IMPORTANT FACTOR IN TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGES

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Linguopragmatic competence is considered as a part of pragmatic competence. Pragmatic competence generally refers to the ability of language participants to use language appropriately and contextually in communicative situations. It includes understanding and following the social, cultural and pragmatic rules of the language. Linguopragmatic competence is a special aspect of pragmatic competence, aimed at using language tools (lexical, grammatical and syntactic structures) in a contextually appropriate manner to achieve specific communicative goals. In other words, linguopragmatic competence emphasizes the linguistic aspects of pragmatic language use. For example, selecting and using specific linguistic tools to perform speech acts (such as compliments, requests, or apologies) falls under linguopragmatic competence. While linguopragmatic competence is a component of pragmatic competence, it specifically focuses on the specialized skills related to the pragmatic use of language.

V.S. Li emphasizes the importance of studying linguopragmatic competence as follows: learning a foreign language, as is known, is associated with the formation of communicative competence. In a narrow sense, language competence is understood as knowing the units of all levels of the language and the rules for using them to form and understand any speech structures. In a broad sense, linguistic competence means a person's ability to communicate in real-life situations. Although this concept may seem self-evident, it encompasses various aspects of speech and speech-thinking (discursive) activity, therefore it is necessary to consider several types of communicative competence, the most important of which is linguopragmatic competence. This type of competence represents a set of skills and abilities that determine the choice of strategy and tactics of speech behavior in specific communication situations in order to successfully implement communicative intentions.[3]

Yu.G. Davidova gives the following definition of linguopragmatic competence: linguopragmatic competence is an important component of communicative competence, the acquisition of which ensures the success of intercultural communication, facilitates mutual understanding between representatives of different cultures, and prevents the formation of negative stereotypes. Taking into account the socio-cultural context in which

communication takes place, the values of the foreign language culture, pragmatic norms and rules, using strategies of polite communicative behavior, the ability to correctly interpret the connotative components of lexical units and the meaning of speech helps to avoid pragmalinguistic failures that arise due to differences in language systems, differences in communicative behavior, and differences in socio-cultural values.[1]

According to H. Paluanova, linguopragmatic competence allows language learners to manage complex social relationships, which increases their ability to express themselves correctly and interpret subtle gestures in communication. The integration of linguopragmatic principles into ELT programs develops the ability to go beyond the grammatical correctness of the language, to interpret the context and participate in meaningful communication.[4]

I.G. Kazumyan argues that communicative linguopragmatic competence is also the ability to engage in intercultural communication. Two main components of linguopragmatic competence are distinguished:

Discursive competence - the ability to build whole and logically connected statements in oral and written speech, the ability to choose the necessary form and method of expression depending on the conditions of the speech act, such as the situation, intention and communicative goal of the speaker. Discursive competence includes the skills of starting a conversation, changing the topic of discussion or the direction of the dialogue, politely entering into a conversation, ending the dialogue, etc.

Functional competence is the ability to achieve the intentions and goals for which a communicative act is performed, knowledge of typical communicative interaction schemes (question - answer, message - consent / non-consent, request - refusal, etc.), the ability to correctly interpret the information received - orally or in writing, the ability to express one's opinion, surprise, interest, sympathy and other feelings, to express one's intentions (directly or indirectly). [2]

Yu. G. Davidova believes that students are not sufficiently aware of the components of this competence. They make mistakes in choosing formal / normative and informal speech registers, do not use all pragmatic and cultural behavioral strategies of the language, do not fully use the means of communication and integrity of speech. The need to improve all components of linguopragmatic competence determines its relevance.[1]

Therefore, in order to successfully use language in context, it is necessary not only to master the language grammatically, but also to master the knowledge of its correct use.

Used literature

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